

The Impact of Time Management on Primary Learners' Engagement in Blended Learning Tasks

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the impact of time management on engagement of primary learners in blended learning tasks. The study employed a correlational research design to investigate, analyze, and discover the relationship of the time management of primary learners in blended learning tasks to their behavioral, cognitive and emotional engagement as observed by their parents and teachers. The study included 80 parents and 30 teachers from three elementary schools in Cavite with a total of 120 respondents. The findings revealed that both teachers and parents generally agree that primary learners manage their time to a moderate extent in blended learning tasks. The learners show strong emotional engagement, reflecting motivation, interest, and emotional connection to learning. However, their cognitive and behavioral engagement levels are only moderate, suggesting that while students are emotionally invested, they may need additional support to manage tasks independently and engage more deeply in learning activities. Additionally, the findings indicate no significant difference between teachers' and parents' assessments of primary learners' time management in blended learning tasks, whether in modular or face-to-face settings. Furthermore, the findings indicate a significant positive relationship between time management and the level of engagement among primary

learners in both modular and face-to-face learning settings. Time management significantly influences primary learners' behavioral and cognitive engagement. Face-to-face learning shows a stronger impact in these areas particularly in emotional engagement. The extent of time management in blended learning tasks significantly influences primary learners' ability to manage their time and complete academic activities effectively across different learning modalities. It can be concluded that time management plays a crucial role in enhancing primary learners' engagement across various dimensions—behavioral, cognitive, and emotional—in both modular and face-to-face learning environments and in shaping the academic engagement and self-regulation skills of primary learners in blended learning environments. It is recommended that educators and schools incorporate more structured routines, clear expectations, and consistent teacher support in blended learning environments. This could include regular check-ins, time management workshops, and the use of visual schedules or reminders to help learners stay on track. Furthermore, schools may consider utilizing the Elago's Teachers and Parents' Involvement (TPI) Framework to improve the academic performance of students in both face-to-face and modular learning modalities.

Keywords: *behavioral engagement, blended learning tasks, cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, and time management*

INTRODUCTION

Student engagement was one of the prime mechanisms by which a learner's lessons could be fostered effectively. Student engagement ensures that the information being absorbed by learners is reinforced and integrated effectively. Knowledge retention, feedback assessment, and real-life application are all driven by the level of student engagement within the learning space, whether it be in a physical classroom or through blended learning means. The level of engagement of a learner was also significantly associated with their level of interest in the subject matter and their overall academic performance as a whole. While an array of variables might clash with their interest and performance, how they engaged with the material at hand could greatly lead to their retention and application of that knowledge.

Primary education involves learners who must be engaged throughout the learning process. Effective strategies in learner engagement and classroom management require the attention of teachers in the processes they instill inside the four corners of the room (Franklin & Harrington, 2019). Various interventions are created by primary school teachers, such as the implementation of the 3E model (Enhance, Extend, and Empower) as well as having KWL (What I Know, Want to Know, and What I Learned) and POE (Predict-Observe-Explain) techniques (Koto et al., 2019). These methods proved to be effective in facilitating student. Engagement is an integral part of the learning process of students at the primary level.

Time management is an essential arsenal as a learner traverses the increasing levels of schooling. From balancing several different subjects at once to managing group work, individual outputs, and exercises, and independent reading, the way a learner manages their time influences the way they absorb the lessons coming from their schools. However, the tendency of someone to prioritize time management was ultimately interlinked with how they are engaging with the course and subject content, alongside the simple fact of whether or not a learner is inside a classroom with other peers or at their own homes, alone, with the freedom to take up the information in whatever pace they please. This disparity between learning modalities was amplified by the current conditions of the learning paradigm, with the after-effects of the COVID-19 pandemic in the way we structured the lessons and information for the students.

One can infer that the level of engagement of a learner would influence their time management abilities, but further work in finding a correlation between the two needs to be sought. Valle et al. (2019) mentioned that a significant portion of the existing studies on schoolwork focused on analyzing time management in homework and its effects on academic performance. They deduced that make worse time management, the more time it would take to accomplish specific tasks and foster academic success. However, an aspect such as that of student engagement isn't often taken into account as a driver in the way a learner manages their time.

Comprehending how primary school learners' engagement influenced their management of time with consideration for whether the learning environment was synchronous or asynchronous, can allow us to determine courses of action for improvements in engagement in class. The researcher also aimed to outline and reveal ideas regarding student engagement and how we could better hone the abilities and skills of primary-level learners. Blended learning environments would be taken into account in the creation of programs and possible solutions to particularize the situations of each learner.

An analysis of blended learning environments and how this affects one's time management skills was a segment that must be accounted for. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, blended learning and distance education were tools that were mainly used in international educational programs (Klenner et al., 2017). However, we have seen its incremental integration into the education system in various countries. In higher education, there has been an increased consideration of using blended learning wherein students watch

video lectures sourced from massive online open courses (MOOCs) before any face-to-face engagements are done in class (Perez- Sanagustin et al., 2020).

Blended learning had been harnessed across different countries as a byproduct of the COVID-19 pandemic; educational institutions across the world were forced to accustom to the online learning environment setup, eventually proving the method to be effective. While there are still lapses in educators being equipped with the necessary tools to engage in online synchronous classes such as in online platforms to be used and in physical equipment like laptops, cellphones, and other essential gadgets for distance learning (Ventayen, 2019), online education—as we've seen in the past couple of years—was able to foster a learning environment that fit the needs of a learner from the comfort of their own homes. Thus, blended learning environments still need to be taken into account as a now- common mode of education. Learners perceive blended classes as ultimately being interesting, although with a level of apprehensiveness due to concerns about motivation, English language skills, and finally, time management (Fidalgo et al., 2020).

There is this preconceived notion that time management needs to be taught instead of having it be manifested through a learner's means, but the opposite shows up in studies. In a study on how time management affects computational thinking learning in third and fourth graders in Taiwan (Chen et al., 2023), a group that was guided by teachers in the area of learning and time management had significantly lower scores in algorithmic ability and learning motivation than the self-regulated group, which did things on their own pace.

Taking a look at how student engagement affects time management in blended learning on elementary learners could allow us to trace its relationship and how it could create more systematic and organized measures for learners.

Furthermore, acknowledging the benefits of honing skills in learners, such as their self-regulatory techniques and overall time management, could help in narrowing the scope to simply how private primary school learners are affected by their level of engagement inside and outside of the classroom.

In this context, the researcher was interested in exploring the impact of learners' level of engagement on blended learning tasks of primary school learners in private schools. As part of the research locale's teaching force, the researcher observed the importance of time engagement of learners to given tasks to grasp and understand the lesson. How different levels of this engagement impact or affect the level of understanding remains a mystery.

This study aimed to examine the perspectives of teachers and parents regarding the time management practices of primary learners in completing blended learning tasks, and how these practices influenced student engagement. Specifically, it sought to explore the cognitive, behavioral, and emotional dimensions of learner engagement as shaped by home-based task completion and in-school performance. The data gathered informed the development of a collaborative framework between teachers and parents, aimed at enhancing students' time management skills, engagement levels, and overall academic outcomes in public elementary schools implementing blended learning modalities. The research paradigm identified **the time management of primary learners**, as supervised by parents at home and monitored by teachers in the classroom, as the **independent variable**, while **learner engagement**—encompassing cognitive, behavioral, and emotional aspects—serves as the **dependent variable**, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

LITERATURE REVIEW

Blended learning combines traditional teaching with digital tools to create a flexible, engaging, and learner-centered environment. It aims to equip students—especially in primary schools—with the skills they need for success in today’s digital society. This review explores recent studies on blended learning practices and student engagement, particularly in public education.

Boubih et al. (2023) investigated what influences student engagement in Moroccan schools. Their study of 248 learners (ages 13–18) found that engagement increases with strong peer support, clear academic goals, positive relationships with teachers, and family involvement. Interestingly, age and gender affected engagement—girls generally participated more actively—while socioeconomic factors had little impact.

In a separate study, Lin et al. (2019) explored how students performed in a fully online flipped classroom. They found that watching pre-recorded lectures and participating actively in online sessions improved learning outcomes. Students who showed up on time and used webcams also interacted more and received better grades, highlighting the importance of digital readiness and self-motivation in online learning.

Kelly and Lock (2021) focused on curriculum design in blended settings. They emphasized that strong teacher presence—even without live interaction—can boost student support and engagement. Their findings showed that consistent feedback and accessible content helped students feel connected, especially

in asynchronous or remote learning environments. This was particularly important during the pandemic, when many students faced online learning for the first time.

Together, these studies suggest that blended and online learning can be effective if designed thoughtfully. Key factors include teacher presence, student support systems, flexible delivery modes, and access to meaningful learning tasks.

Camilleri (2021) discussed the shift in higher education from traditional and blended learning to fully virtual delivery due to the COVID-19 pandemic. As institutions were forced to adopt social distancing and health protocols, they rapidly transitioned to remote instruction. The paper emphasized that virtual learning systems are likely to remain in place post-pandemic and encouraged educational leaders to embrace this change. It also provided insights for educators and identified areas for future research. The pandemic accelerated the adoption of flexible learning—using both digital and non-digital tools—to ensure continued access to education. Santiago et al. (2021) explored this shift among students at Cavite State University – Silang Campus (CvSU-SC). Their study, involving 364 students through an online survey, found that smartphones and mobile apps were the most used learning tools. Google Classroom was the preferred platform for asynchronous learning, while Google Meet was widely used for synchronous classes. Students reported being generally competent in using digital learning platforms.

Social media, particularly Facebook, was seen as practical, while Google and Zoom were viewed as accessible and user-friendly. The research highlighted that learner readiness was a key factor for effective online participation. It also stressed the need for more tailored, student-centered digital content to enhance the quality of teaching and learning during flexible instruction. Almoslamani (2018) examined engagement in Saudi Arabia's blended learning context using LMS data from 246 students at the Saudi Electronic University. While no significant gender differences were found in overall participation or academic performance, male and female students differed in how they perceived their weekly time spent on LMS tasks. The study suggested that integrating multimedia tools, such as audio discussions and video conferencing, could enhance student engagement and critical thinking in LMS environments.

Overall, these findings underline the importance of learner readiness, platform accessibility, and interactive content in promoting successful flexible learning—both during and beyond the pandemic. Seemingly, Fabriz, Mendzheritskaya, and Stehle (2021) agreed that universities were challenged by the COVID-19 pandemic's sudden effects to offer their learners online teaching and learning environments that were both immediately applicable and conducive to high-quality learning. As a result, there was a wide range of synchronous and asynchronous online learning and teaching environments. Some courses provided a balance between the two, while others focused primarily on synchronous or asynchronous teaching and learning.

As such, they investigated whether a predominance of synchronous or asynchronous teaching and learning settings in higher education was associated with specific student experiences and outcomes in a survey study involving students ($N = 3,056$) and teachers ($N = 396$) from a large German university. They also looked at how well these two kinds of teaching and learning environments meet the self-determination theory's (SDT) basic psychological needs of learners for relatedness, competence, and autonomy. Following the first online semester, data were gathered because of the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings suggest that, from the viewpoint of the learners, there are differences between the two teaching and learning environments in terms of how well the methods support social interaction and fundamental psychological needs as suggested by SDT. Compared to learners who studied primarily in asynchronous environments, those who studied primarily in synchronous settings reported higher levels of peer-centered activities like feedback.

Recent studies have explored how different teaching formats—synchronous, asynchronous, and blended—affect student engagement, satisfaction, and psychological well-being. Findings show that teachers saw little difference between synchronous and asynchronous methods in terms of feedback activities. However, students in synchronous settings reported higher support for their psychological

needs, such as relatedness and competence, and expressed greater satisfaction with their learning experience. Overall, learners who felt their psychological needs were met and were more open to using technology reported more positive outcomes, suggesting key considerations for post-pandemic teaching (Lima, Lautert, & Gomes, 2021).

In Brazil, Lima et al. (2021) conducted an experimental study comparing engagement levels in blended versus traditional learning environments. Ninety-two 10th-grade students participated in lessons that combined lectures with computer-assisted activities. Despite differing levels of familiarity with technology, students consistently showed higher engagement in blended settings. Using screen recordings to measure behavioral engagement, the researchers found that students were more actively involved in lessons with digital components. These results underline the importance of interactive, tech-supported teaching in boosting classroom engagement.

Ramchand, Khunyakari, and Bose (2023) reviewed literature on virtual learning environments through a constructivist lens, emphasizing that students build their own knowledge through active engagement. Drawing from engagement theory, which focuses on motivation and participation, their review confirmed that learner involvement and interest are essential for success in online education. These findings reinforce the value of designing digital learning environments that support both autonomy and interaction.

The review employs a methodical approach to locate and examine pertinent research on the relationship between academic achievement and virtual learning environments, as well as student engagement. Both a manual search of reference lists and an extensive search of electronic databases are part of the search strategy. Conclusions: The review emphasized the advantages of virtual learning environments for academic success and student engagement. Based on the analysis, it could be concluded that virtual learning environments provide a range of features and resources that could improve students' engagement, motivation, and motivation to learn. Furthermore, the research indicated that virtual learning environments had the potential to offer learners a more customized and adaptable learning environment. On the part of Shenkut, Atnafu, and Michael (2023), analyzed how the blended learning approach affects the algebra learning engagement of ninth-grade secondary school students. A pretest-posttest non-equivalent group quasi-experimental design was used in this investigation. Using a mathematics engagement questionnaire, data were gathered from ninth-grade learners and subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), paired sample t-test, mean, and standard deviation. The findings showed that not all student groups had the same overall level of engagement with algebra. Regarding the aspects of students' engagement with learning algebra, a noteworthy distinction was noted between the groups. Additionally, the use of blended learning and problem-solving techniques increased learners' interest in learning algebra. Additionally, compared to the learners in the problem-solving group and the comparison group, the blended learning group's students showed higher levels of algebraic learning engagement. Lastly, we suggest that more research be done to look at how to improve student engagement and its various dimensions in various subjects.

Molina-Cristobal et al (2021) claimed that to provide students with a flexible learning framework, blended learning combines in-person instruction in the classroom with virtual learning opportunities. Most people agree that face-to-face instruction was more engaging. Online resources, on the other hand, provide learners more freedom and flexibility in how they approach their studies and can serve as an extra tool to reinforce and improve content that was taught face-to-face. Self-determination theory and the concepts of emotional and cognitive engagement have drawn interest as potential frameworks for characterizing and influencing blended learning student engagement.

According to a recent survey conducted by the University of Glasgow Singapore (UGS), learners feel that using online resources is beneficial, and they recommend that 40–60% of teaching experiences should be online or video-based. Optimizing student engagement through online content, format, and delivery was crucial. Nevertheless, there is a lack of best practice guidelines and disagreement over the optimal structure and ratio between traditional face-to-face (F2F) settings and online work to attain this goal. Hence, their study's goal was to create a set of experimental online resources for four different

engineering programs, get learners' input via structured questionnaires, and determine which metrics and enablers boost student engagement. Their paper presents the results of the learner preference questionnaires and identifies formats and content that are most effectively accessed through online sources. Specifically, their results show that recorded video tutorials combined with in-person lectures are an effective way to raise student engagement and satisfaction.

Villa et al. (2023) cited Sousa (2016) as saying that student engagement was defined as the level of focus, curiosity, interest, and strong emotional bonds that learners had when they were learning, whether in a classroom setting or on their own. The purpose of their study would be to ascertain how engaged the learners were with Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE). A survey was administered to St. Paul University Surigao junior high school learners who were chosen at random. The researcher concluded that the learners had a high level of behavioral, cognitive, and emotional engagement with TLE in a blended learning environment based on the findings.

Additionally, it would determine that there is no significant correlation between the respondents' level of engagement and their age, sex, or grades. As a research result, it was advised that teachers keep creating assignments and activities that would help learners learn TLE while putting a greater emphasis on their cognitive engagement. Teachers may be used as respondents in cross-validation studies of a similar nature, with the inclusion of extra variables. Similarly, Buchan and Precey (2023) delved into the realities of Blended learning as a dynamic and intricate shift in education that required further study to maximize student engagement and create best practices. The explanatory variables of the degree of student engagement in a reputable English higher education institution are investigated using a mixed methods approach. Students are categorized as having "High," "Medium," or "Low" levels of engagement with the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) based on the number of days during the semester that the median student accessed the platform ($n = 562$).

According to the findings, effective blended learning courses include more formative assessments and more recordings, are delivered in a manner that best suits the learner cohort (remote, in-person, or hybrid), and have more high-quality resources on the VLE than quantity. Module leaders should have a strong grasp of the educational technology at their disposal, be highly enthusiastic about the subject matter, and integrate both didactic teaching and active learning into their seminars and lectures to maximize student engagement. It could be concluded that by changing the way Module Leaders designed and conducted their blended learning classes, we might bring about a change in the direction of increased student engagement. Senior leaders could learn a lot from this, including how to better understand blended learning, how it aligns with their mission and values, and what tactics to employ to promote and organize best practices. Buan et al. (2024) opined that an increasing number of higher education institutions are drawn to the use of blended and distance learning approaches because of their potential to improve student enhancement. Research indicated that there was a chance that this method of delivering instruction would boost student interest. The purpose of this study is to identify the essential components of a blended learning environment that maintain student engagement. A descriptive survey would be administered to 123 student teachers at a state university in Mindanao, accompanied by qualitative feedback. For one semester, these participants were enrolled in a blended learning course offered via the Moodle platform. Through the use of a survey questionnaire, the participants evaluated their actual and preferred learning experiences in the context of a blended learning environment and thought back on the activities that encouraged or inhibited participation.

The results show that the experiences that student teachers really had in the blended learning setting closely matched their desired experiences. Within the framework of blended learning, three key elements—relevance, interactivity, and connectedness—came to light as being crucial to maintaining engagement.

The dissertation "*The Impact of Time Management of Primary Learners on Their Engagement in Blended Learning Tasks*" explores how student engagement influences the success of blended learning in

public primary schools. It draws from recent studies to examine key factors affecting engagement, the transition to blended learning, and the role of different teaching formats.

Boubih et al. (2023) highlighted the importance of cognitive and psychological engagement, showing that strong teacher-student relationships, peer support, and students' future goals boost motivation. Age and gender also influenced engagement levels. The COVID-19 pandemic forced schools to adopt remote and blended learning. Camilleri (2021) emphasized the shift to virtual teaching and the lasting role of technology in education. Lin et al. (2019) and Kelly and Lock (2021) supported the effectiveness of flipped classrooms and asynchronous learning, showing that flexible, digital instruction can promote engagement even without live interaction. Fabric et al. (2021) found that synchronous settings support learners' psychological needs better than asynchronous ones, leading to greater satisfaction and performance. This is especially relevant for tailoring blended environments to young learners. Studies by Lima et al. (2021) and Shenkut et al. (2023) showed that blended learning improves engagement, particularly in subjects like math. A balanced mix of traditional and digital methods can enhance learning outcomes. However, Celestino and Noronha (2021) and Akhter et al. (2021) noted challenges such as the need for self-discipline, time management, and stable internet access. These factors must be addressed to ensure equity and effectiveness. In conclusion, research supports the idea that well-designed blended learning can improve engagement and academic performance in primary schools. Key strategies include fostering supportive relationships, using flexible technologies, and designing accessible and engaging learning tasks tailored to young learners' needs.

Statement of the Problem

The study's goal was to assess how teachers and parents perceived the impact of blended learning activities for primary school learners in public schools, where there was a greater opportunity to experiment with alternative approaches to enhancing learning outcomes. Public schools' unique resources and infrastructure enabled them to optimize learning environments by fine-tuning blended learning assignments with the relevant competencies.

Specifically, this study aimed to address the following research questions:

1. What was the extent of time management of primary learners on their engagement in the blended learning tasks in terms of:
 - 1.1 Modular learning; and
 - 1.2 Face-to-Face activities?
2. What was the level of engagement of the primary learners on the blended learning tasks as assessed by the two groups of respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 behavioral;
 - 2.2 cognitive; and
 - 2.3 emotional?
3. Was there a significant difference in the extent of time management on the blended learning tasks of the primary learners as assessed by the respondents?
4. Was there a significant difference in the level of student engagement of the primary learners as assessed by the two groups of respondents?
5. Was there a significant relationship between the extent of time management and the level of student engagement of the primary learners on blended learning?

6. Did the extent of time management on the blended learning tasks have an impact on the level of time management of primary learners?
7. Based on the results of the findings, what might be proposed to improve the learning engagement of primary learners?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a correlational research design to examine the relationship between the perspectives and experiences of teachers and parents regarding primary learners' time management and its influence on student engagement in blended learning tasks. A researcher-developed survey instrument was employed to assess key variables, including parental involvement and supervision, teachers' technological proficiency, and instructional strategies, in relation to learner engagement and academic outcomes. This design, as outlined by Dawadi, Shrestha, and Giri (2021), enabled the investigation of statistical relationships without manipulating variables, thus providing insights into naturally occurring patterns. The study involved a total of 120 participants, comprising 80 parents of primary learners and 30 teachers from three public elementary schools: Timalan Hillview Integrated School, Ciudad Nuevo Elementary School, and Petronilo L. Torres Memorial Elementary School. Participants were selected through purposive sampling, based on their availability and willingness to participate. While this method facilitated focused data collection within the study's logistical constraints, it also limited the generalizability of findings to broader populations. The voluntary nature of participation, combined with resource and time limitations, was acknowledged as a constraint to the wider applicability of the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following is the summary of the findings of the study:

1. The findings indicated that both teachers and parents generally agreed that primary learners managed their time to a moderate extent in blended learning tasks. However, learners' time management was consistently rated higher in face-to-face settings compared to modular learning. This suggests that the structure, routine, and direct supervision provided in face-to-face environments play a positive role in helping primary learners manage their time more effectively. It could be concluded that while primary learners are generally able to manage their time to a moderate extent in blended learning tasks, face-to-face learning environments are perceived by both teachers and parents as more effective in fostering time management skills. The higher ratings for face-to-face modality suggest that its structured setting, consistent routines, and direct supervision provide an optimal environment for developing learners' time management abilities. This highlights the importance of maintaining elements of structure and teacher-guided support in any learning modality to enhance learners' ability to manage their time efficiently.
2. The findings revealed that primary learners in blended learning environments show strong emotional engagement, reflecting motivation, interest, and emotional connection to learning. However, their cognitive and behavioral engagement levels are only moderate, suggesting that while students are emotionally invested, they might need additional support to manage tasks independently and engage more deeply in learning activities. The study highlights the importance of structured guidance to strengthen these areas. The conclusion drawn from these findings was that while primary learners in blended learning environments are highly emotionally engaged, there was a need for more targeted instructional strategies that foster higher cognitive and behavioral engagement. Emotional engagement served as a foundation for motivation, but learners require additional support to effectively manage learning tasks and engage in critical

thinking and active participation. Therefore, a more balanced approach, incorporating strategies that stimulate cognitive and behavioral engagement, was crucial for holistic learner development.

3. The findings indicated no significant difference between teachers' and parents' assessments of primary learners' time management in blended learning tasks, whether in modular or face-to-face settings. This suggests that both groups perceive learners' time management abilities in a similar way across both learning modalities. The conclusion drawn from these findings was that there was a consensus between teachers and parents regarding the time management of primary learners in blended learning tasks, regardless of the modality. The lack of significant differences in assessments between these two groups implies that both teachers and parents observed similar patterns of time management in their children's learning, whether it was through modular or face-to-face learning formats.
4. The findings indicated a significant positive relationship between time management and the level of engagement among primary learners in both modular and face-to-face learning settings. This suggested that better time management is associated with higher behavioral, cognitive, and emotional engagement across both modalities. The conclusion drawn from these findings was that time management plays a crucial role in enhancing primary learners' engagement across various dimensions—behavioral, cognitive, and emotional—in both modular and face-to-face learning environments. Effective time management practices seem to contribute to more active participation, deeper thinking, and greater emotional investment in learning tasks.
5. The findings revealed that time management in both modular and face-to-face modalities significantly influenced primary learners' behavioral and cognitive engagement. Face-to-face learning showed a stronger impact in these areas. While emotional engagement was also significantly affected by time management in face-to-face settings, it does not show a significant impact in modular learning. The conclusion drawn from these findings was that time management plays a critical role in fostering engagement in primary learners, particularly in terms of behavioral and cognitive aspects, across both learning modalities. While both modalities significantly affect learners' engagement in these areas, the emotional aspect was significantly influenced only in the "Face-to-Face" modality. The findings suggest that structured time management, particularly in the "Face-to-Face" modality, had a more pronounced effect on engaging learners emotionally, which was not the case in the "Modular" modality.
6. The extent of time management in blended learning tasks significantly influences primary learners' ability to manage their time and complete academic activities effectively across different learning modalities. When tasks are well-structured and time-bound, learners are more likely to develop essential skills such as Time management played a crucial role in shaping the academic engagement and self-regulation skills of primary learners in blended learning environments. Well-designed learning tasks that encourage time awareness and accountability foster the development of effective study habits, enabling learners to become more autonomous and motivated in managing their academic responsibilities.
7. Both parents and teachers recognized that while modular and face-to-face learning modalities influence students' engagement, face-to-face learning provides a more significant positive impact on learners' active participation and involvement in class activities.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations culled from the conclusions of the study.

1. The school may try utilizing The Elago's Teachers, and Parents' Involvement (TPI) Framework to improve the academic performance of the students in both faces to face and modular learning modality.

2. To enhance primary learners' time management skills across all learning modalities, it was recommended that educators and schools incorporate more structured routines, clear expectations, and consistent teacher support in blended learning environments. This could include regular check-ins, time management workshops, and the use of visual schedules or reminders to help learners stay on track. Additionally, integrating elements from the face-to-face modality—such as timely feedback, direct supervision, and interactive activities—into blended and modular learning tasks may further improve students' ability to manage their time effectively. By combining the strengths of both modalities, educators could create a balanced and supportive learning environment that nurtures better time management skills for all learners.
3. It was recommended that parents and teachers foster stronger collaboration to ensure consistent support for students' time management skills across both learning modalities. Since both groups share similar perceptions, joint efforts in providing structured guidance and strategies could help improve students' time management abilities. This might include regular communication about learning progress, creating routines, and providing practical time management tools that could be used both at home and in the classroom.
4. It was recommended that school leaders could integrate time management training into the curriculum, offer structured schedules, and provide regular feedback to help learners better organize their time. By fostering these skills, educators could help students improve their engagement in all aspects of learning, leading to better academic outcomes. The curriculum planners should design blended learning tasks that are structured, time-bound, and goal-oriented to promote primary learners' time management skills. Integrating clear deadlines, progress monitoring, and opportunities for self-reflection within learning activities could help strengthen learners' ability to manage their time effectively and engage more meaningfully in both modular and face-to-face learning settings.
5. Schools should prioritize opportunities for face-to-face learning or integrate more interactive and structured elements into modular learning to enhance student engagement. Providing clear guidance, regular feedback, and opportunities for social interaction could help bridge the engagement gap between the two modalities.

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